

EFFECT OF WASTE WATER ON CONCRETE AND STEEL

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ABSTRACT

In an age of increasing human population and dwindling resources, coupled with the need to curb expenditure in various sectors of the government budget, attention has been brought to the re-use of resources wherever possible. Perhaps, one of the most valuable resources in India is water. Therefore, effort towards waste water re-use has lately gained worldwide consideration and attention.

This paper presents the mechanical properties of concrete mixed using industrial waste water and also explains how treated waste water can be used in construction industry and reduces the load on nature. The impurities present in water can affect the properties of concrete and steel when used for mixing in concrete. Also the impurities may not affect all properties of concrete and steel but some.

KEYWORDS- dwindling resources, reuse of waste water, construction industry.